

Optimization of Silver-Coated Boehmite Nanostructures for Enhanced SERS detection of date-rape drugs

G. Geka¹, F. Kalogeropoulou¹, A. Kanioura¹, M. Angelopoulou¹, S. Richardson², A. Dimitriou², D. Tsounidi³, I. Raptis³, D. Goustouridis³, N. Papanikolaou², S. Kakabakos¹, P. Petrou¹

¹Institute of Nuclear & Radiological Sciences & Technology, Energy & Safety, NCSR “Demokritos, Agia Paraskevi, Greece

²Institute of Nanoscience & Nanotechnology, NCSR “Demokritos”, Agia Paraskevi, Greece

³ThetaMetrisis, S.A., 12132, Athens, Greece

E-mail: ypetrou@rrp.demokritos.gr

The problem

Gamma hydroxybutyrate acid (GHB) is an anesthetic drug for the treatment of narcolepsy;

GHB also **occurs naturally in the human brain**, acting like a neurotransmitter and stimulating dopamine release.

GHB came to be used recreationally, especially at raves and clubs, gaining notoriety as the “***date rape drug***” – due to its ability to **incapacitate victims prior to a sexual assault**.

Available in powder or liquid form **without odor** and **minimal taste**, ***small quantities of the drug*** can lead to ***euphoria***; however ***higher doses*** of GHB can also lead to ***respiratory depression, coma,*** and ***bradycardia***.

Since 2001 GHB has been **under international control** and was added to Schedule IV of the United Nations Convention on Psychotropic Substances 1971, ceasing the open sale of GHB. However, its **precursors – gamma-butyrolactone and 1,4-butanediol – were not listed as international controlled substances**, increasing the concerns related to their illicit use.

Available solutions

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (golden standard for forensic use), Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (widely accepted for forensic use) High-Performance Liquid Chromatography, Headspace Gas Chromatography, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance, Capillary Electrophoresis (CE) Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS), Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy

PROS: Sensitive, Simultaneous detection of GHB, GHB-precursors

CONS: Expensive, lab-bound instruments, technically demanding sample preparation

Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA)

PROS: Sensitive, analysis of many samples, less expensive

CONS: lab-bound method, requires confirmation with GC-MS or LC-MS

Paper-Based Microfluidic Analytical Devices (μ PAD), Chromo and Fluorogenic Detection

PROS: Suitable for on-site detection of GHB

CONS: Lower sensitivity, accuracy affected by biological fluid interference, limited forensic acceptance, requires confirmation

Surface-enhanced Raman Spectroscopy

Label-Free SERS Detection

Biological & Biomedical Applications

Biomolecules

Pathogens

Living cells

Tissues

Body fluids

Drugs

- ✓ Non-invasive technique
- ✓ Minimal background interference
- ✓ High sensitivity (single molecule detection)
- ✓ Direct or indirect detection (using labels)

Zheng X.-S. , et al, Spectrochim. Acta A 197 (2018) 56-77,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2018.01.063>.

Surface-enhanced Raman Spectroscopy

Wang, B. X., et al, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutrition* 64 (2022) 472–516. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2022.2106547>

EUROP(T)RODE 2026, MARCH 29 – APRIL 1, JENA

Preparation of SERS substrates

Interference fringes appear due to different refractive indexes of the different layers leading to multiple internal light reflections.

As the Ag increases up to 80 nm a small red shift of the interference fringes with respect to bare boehmite is observed

For Ag thickness over 80 nm the substrates are becoming opaque and therefore the fringes faint.

Preparation of SERS substrates

Interference fringes appear due to different refractive indexes of the different layers leading to multiple internal light reflections.

As the Ag increases up to 80 nm a small red shift of the interference fringes with respect to bare boehmite is observed

For Ag thickness over 80 nm the substrates are becoming opaque and therefore the fringes faint.

Evaluation of SERS substrates

Rhodamine 6G

Raman spectra of Rhodamine 6G acquired on a bare silicon wafer (a=1 μ M, b=10 μ M) and silver coated wafers (c=0.1 μ M). Inset: Raman spectra in dependence on R6G concentration.

Halouzka V. et al J. Electrochem. Soc. 160 (2013) B54, DOI 10.1149/2.003306jes

Evaluation of SERS substrates

Uric acid

https://sersitive.eu/application_types/results-obtained-by-our-customers/uric-acid/

Evaluation of SERS substrates

Renishaw inVia™
Confocal Raman microscope
Laser 785 nm
10 mW
0.5 s acquisition time
30 measurements/sample
with a $\times 20$ objective lens

5- μL solution left to dry

Evaluation of SERS substrates - Rhodamine 6G

Rhodamine 6G
solution in
water 10⁻⁶ M

Evaluation of SERS substrates - Rhodamine 6G

612 cm^{-1}

1650 cm^{-1}

Evaluation of SERS substrates – Uric acid

Evaluation of SERS substrates

Calculation of the Enhancement Factor (EF)

$$EF = \frac{I_{SERS}/(P_{SERS} \times T_{SERS} \times N_{SERS})}{I_{RS}/(P_{RS} \times T_{RS} \times N_{RS})}$$

Where:

I_{SERS} is the analyte Raman scattering intensity on SERS-active substrates

I_{RS} is the Raman intensity from the analyte deposited on a non-enhancing surface (plain Si wafer)

P_{SERS} and P_{RS} represent the power of the excitation laser (same for SERS-active and non-active substrates)

T_{SERS} and T_{RS} are the acquisition times for each case respectively

$$N_{RS} = \left[\left(\frac{(\text{confocal volume} \times \text{Density})}{\text{molecular weight}} \right) \times \text{Avogadro's number} (N_A) \right]$$

$$N_{SERS} = \left[\left(\frac{\text{Laser spot area}}{\text{Substrate area}} \right) \times \text{volume} (V) \times \text{concentration} (C) \right]$$

Evaluation of SERS substrates

Application of the substrates developed

Build-up of a in-house low cost and size instrument for measurements in flow

γ -hydroxybutyric acid (GHB)

Future application of the substrates developed

Raman system

- Laser input
- ×10 Objective lens
- Filters
- Spectrometer output

Microfluidic chip

- SERS sensor
- PMMA cover
- Tubes for liquid flow

Tube

- Moves up and down

Rotation stage

- 4 different liquid positions

Application of the substrates developed

Application of the substrates developed

Implementation of **ML signal processing algorithms** to discriminate GHB signal from the background

Conclusions

SERS substrates were prepared on silicon wafers covered with an aluminium layer via thermal treatment at aqueous environment to partially oxidize the aluminium layer creating boehmite nanostructures on top of which silver is deposited by sputtering.

Substrates prepared using different parameters for silver depositions onto the boehmite nanostructures were evaluated regarding the signal enhancement factor achieved using Rhodamine 6G and uric acid as model substances with known Raman spectrum.

The performance of the substrates prepared was also compared with commercially available substrates bearing silver nanostructures.

Using boehmite substrates covered with 80-nm thick silver layer enhancement factors over 10^7 were achieved for Rhodamine 6G, whereas for uric acid substrates with a 40-nm provided the higher enhancement factor.

The achieved enhancement factors were significantly higher compared to those obtained by commercial substrates.

The substrates are currently employed for the detection of GHB in beverages and biological fluids.

Acknowledgments

ARMADILLO project is funded by the EU Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101168416

Co-funded by
the European Union

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

EUROP(T)RODE 2026, MARCH 29 – APRIL 1, JENA